

Reasoner-Aid Research: Potentials and Popularity

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Abstract

This paper presents the first study on the popularity of reasoner-aid research among students. To understand how students are accepting and conducting research with the help of reasoners, a survey was conducted among students in two Dutch universities. The analysis shows that the majority has little knowledge about this approach and a small amount of students have experience with reasoner-aid research. This paper summarises the benefit of reasoner-aid research, reasons of its limited popularity and discuss the potentials of this approach.

1 Introduction

Since the first use of computers for research to find large prime numbers, computer software and hardware have been playing an important role in research activities. Among them, reasoners have a long history in assisting research activities. Reasoners are programs made to assist theorem proving, verify proofs, find counter examples and test and discover properties of mathematical and logical problems. After decades of development, these programs are more powerful than ever before and capable to free researchers from many repetitive and tedious calculations and reasoning tasks. However, not every mathematician, logician, and computer scientist knows how to use such computer programs to assist their research. Many have never heard about this class of programs and this approach. The project investigates the popularity of reasoners and the gap between the use and the development of reasoners in logic, mathematics and computer science research. This paper presents a qualitative study by summarising the history and recent advances of this approach, and a quantitative analysis by conducting a survey among students about the following question.

How much do mathematics, logic and computer science students know using reasoners in their research?

In this paper, we take a general definition of reasoners. We include all interactive and automatic, domain-specific and general-purpose reasoners, developed or maintained in academia or industry. Despite the development and increasing use of reasoners during the past decades, not many scientists and students know how to use reasoners to assist their research. Moreover, the quality, reliability and usability of these programs are questioned by many.

Hypothesis: For the students in the survey, the majority have little knowledge about this approach and a minority have some limited knowledge and experience with reasoners for research purposes.

This paper is organised as follows. Section 1 summarise the history and recent advances of reasoner-aid research and presents the motivation to conduct the survey. Section 2 is about the method of the survey. Section 3 study the results of the survey and Section 4 further discuss the results and the reasons of its limited popularity.

1.1 Background

Human reasoning has been playing a central role in innovation, especially mathematical and logical research. Deductive reasoning has been considered the key of mathematical and logical research and has

been one of the major interest in psychology and cognitive science for decades [5, 15]. In mathematics and logic, as defined in [15], a formal proof is a finite sequence of sentences in which each sentence is either a premise, an axiom of the logical system, or a sentence that follows from preceding sentences by one of the system's rules. An argument is deducible in the system if there is a proof whose final sentence is the conclusion of the argument. Theorem proving and proof checking are among the main tasks of mathematicians and logicians. Without the aid of computers, proofs are generated and checked manually. Thanks to the development of reasoners over the past decades, some part of these reasoning activities can be automated [1]. Depending on the degree of automation, we distinguish between automated and interactive theorem proving. Once the axioms, inference rules, premises and the argument are specified, if a computer program can carry out the proof without interacting with the user, it is generally considered an automated reasoner or Automated Theorem Prover (ATP). If interaction with a user is necessary, such reasoners are named Interactive Theorem Provers (ITPs), or Proof Assistants. Depending on the system, the inference rules and some axioms are either embedded in a reasoner or specified while producing the proof of a statement or check a proof in a certain setting [9, 16]. The former is considered universal or general-purpose, the latter is more domain specific. While most reasoners are maintained in academia, there are some reasoners involved in solving problems in industry and are supported or maintained by organisations outside of academia or companies.

The past few decades witnessed the development and wide use of reasoners. Reasoners are more user-friendly and able to find harder proofs and faster than before. The proof of four color theorem was formalised in the Coq proof assistant to check the correctness by Georges Gonthier and Benjamin Werner in 2005 [7]. A milestone is the automatically found proof of the Robbins Conjecture and its postprocessing into a human-comprehensible proof [1]. More recently, the Flyspeck project, a collaborative project to produce a complete formal proof of the Kepler Conjecture, was announced completed on August 10, 2014 [8]. In recent years, a large number of proofs were generated and many of them are grouped in libraries. The Mizar Mathematical Library (MML) consists of 50,000 theorems and more than 100,000 premises [1]. A recent evaluation of ATP systems on MML shown that Vampire can reprove 39% of the proofs in MML when necessary premises are selected [1]. Most recently, Machine Learning methods are being used to train theorem provers on existing proofs for better automation of proof discovery [11]. In addition, SAT solver are being use to find counter examples for mathematical hypothesis. For example, Boris Konev and Alexei Lisitsa proved that by encoding the problem of Erdős discrepancy conjecture into Boolean satisfiability and applying SAT solvers, one can obtain a discrepancy 2 sequence of length 1600 and a proof sequence of length 1161 [14]. One of the most popular applications outside of proving mathematical and logical theorems is model checking and verification. Temporal model checkers, Binary Decision Diagram (BDD) solvers, SAT solvers and reasoners of Quantified boolean Formulas (QBF) are playing important roles in these tasks. Recent years, SMT solvers have contributed to the research of many domains including synthetic biology and structural biology [20], social choice theory [6], railway system design [10], etc. Once generated from a reasoner, the correctness of such proofs can be trivial to validate within the system itself. This leads to programs designed specifically to verify proofs. For example, Dedukti [16] is a universal proof checker for this purpose. Recently, there is an increasing interest in modelling human reasoning within automated reasoning systems using answer set programming, abductive logic programming, declarative programming, etc [3, 13]. These logic-based attempts cuts across cognitive modelling based on cognitive architectures, artificial intelligence, logic itself, psychology of reasoning and research design, and connect various disciplines [3]. This logic-based approach has many potentials in empirical research. Scientific knowledge represented in formal languages are with sufficient semantics and less ambiguity [13, 17]. For example, there is an increasing use of ontology for medicine and physiological research such as patient information modelling, cancer research and drug design [2, 12, 19]. A natural extension of this question is the idea of a robot scientist [13]. A prototype work is the robot scientists Adam and Eve [13, 18].

The Netherlands is home to many reasoners (e.g. Automath [4]) as well as users of reasoners. As reasoners get more and more important in research, they appear more and more often in students' research projects. All this lead to a necessary rethink about the role of reasoners and a study about how students are understanding and accepting this approach and using them as tools. This paper is to study the popularity among students in two Dutch universities.

2 Method

2.1 Design

A survey was designed to study mathematics, logic and computer science students' knowledge of reasoners for research. Considering Bachelor's students' research experience is very limited, we study only that of Master's and PhD students in *Universiteit van Amsterdam* (known as University of Amsterdam in English, UvA in short) and the *Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam* (VU University Amsterdam in English, VU in short). More specifically, the survey collected data from Master's students and PhD students registered at the Mathematics department of both universities, the Informatics Institute of UvA, the Computer Science department of VU, as well as the Institute for Logic, Language and Information (ILLC) of UvA. Here, by PhD students, we mean the *promovendi* since in the Dutch education system, PhD students are officially not students. The Master's students within the study domain consists of around 300 students from 10 master programmes of UvA and around 250 students from 9 master programmes of VU. As for doctoral level, there are around 87 students from the Informatics Institute of UvA, 32 from the Mathematics department, and 66 PhD students from ILLC. For VU, there are around 63 PhD students from the Computer Science department and 31 PhD students from the Mathematics department. This study excluded post-doctoral researchers, university researchers with more experience (associate professors, professors, etc) and researchers and engineers in industry. The questions were grouped into three sections. **Section 1** took some general information from the participants: every participant was required to specify if he or she is a Master's student or a PhD student. **Section 2** studied participants' knowledge about this approach. Moreover, the research activities the participants have involved and the reasoners used were asked. **Section 3** collected participants' view about the learning and usability of reasoners as well as the trust of results and willingness to learn more about this approach. More specifically, the three sections of questions were as follows. Most questions were multiple choice questions, except 3a), 3d) and 3e), which were with a linear scale of 1 to 5. Due to the limit of space, a summary of the survey organised by section is as follows. A copy of the complete survey is online at <http://goo.gl/forms/kOTOV38HIPTfJ98e2> and a summary of the survey questions is attached in Appendix A.

2.2 Survey Procedure

The questionnaire was constructed and managed using Google Forms. The survey was conducted from the morning of Tuesday 21st June until Midnight 22nd June. It was spread in two ways. The link to the questionnaire was first posted on Facebook groups of master and PhD students of UvA and VU. Following that, emails were sent to many (randomly selected) PhD students within the study domain. The data was exported to a spreadsheet which is available online at <https://github.com/airobert/C3GI>. This survey method was chosen since many Master's students no longer have courses during this survey. While most PhD students work in their own offices. For this reason, conducting an online survey is less time-consuming compared with a face-to-face approach. More specifically, the survey received 63 responses on the first day and 18 on the second day.

3 Results

The survey obtained 81 responses. Among which, 76 are valid¹. More specifically, 47 participants are Master's students and 29 are PhD students. In other words, around 8.5% of the Master's students participated in the survey and around 10.4% for that of PhD students. Around 61.8% of the participants were Master's students and the rest (around 38.2%) were PhD students. The sample was therefore representative based on the amount of valid entries obtained.

Section 2 consisted of three questions about the participants' knowledge about using reasoners for research. The first question asked about the user's knowledge about reasoners. 43.4% of the participants have never heard about reasoners of any kind and 19.7% know reasoners, but not for research. That was, 48 out of 76 (63.1%) participants knew little or nothing about this approach. An additional 22.4% had some awareness about how a reasoner could help by reading an article, a report or attending a presentation. Only two out of 9 mathematics Master's students had some awareness about this approach. At least 9.2% of those have learnt using a reasoner from courses by the universities and 5.2%

¹Entry 13, 55 and 70 are not within the study domain and entry 56 and 59 are incomplete or self-contradictory. They are filtered out during data analysis.

Figure 1: Amount of Reasoners/Class of Activities

obtained some more knowledge and experience using at least one reasoner for research. Question 2 further studied what the popular reasoners are. The result reflected the findings of Question 1. 56 out of 76 participants have never used any reasoners so far in their studies or research. The most popular reasoners were SAT solvers (13.2%), inductive reasoners (9.2%) and type inference systems (5.3%). Aside from these, MAXSAT solvers, first-order theorem provers, temporal model checkers had a popularity of 3.9% each. Abductive reasoners and BDD solvers were less popular in comparison (2.6% each). Only one student had experience with answer set programming and another student have used higher order theorem prover. No participant had experience with SMT solver, QBF solver or other modal logic solvers (apart from those of temporal logic). Question 3 studied the actual research research tasks involved. Out of 17 valid responses, 7 had experience with model checking using reasoner (around 41.1%), making it the most popular research activity with the reasoners. 5 participants (29.4%) showed that they have used reasoners to prove mathematical theorems and 6 have had experience verifying existing proofs (35.2%). Reasoning about networks (including semantic web) was the fourth most popular research activity in study (4 participants, 23.5%). Robot and agent systems and speech and language technology were equally popular (2 participants each, 11.7%). Another two participants reported their experience with cryptography, type inference in compilers, and finding hard instances of Sudoku, respectively. As for the amount of reasoners these 17 participants have used, most of participants have used less than three reasoners. More specifically, half of them have used only one reasoners for research. 4 of them have experience with 2 reasoners. Another 3 participants have used 3 reasoners. Finally, one has used 4 reasoners so far and another has experience with 7 reasoners in total. By comparing the results of Question 2b) and 2c), as in Figure 1, the amount of reasoners one can use does not determine how many activities the reasoner(s) can be used. For example, one participant can use ASP solvers for both model checking and network reasoning.

Section 3 consisted of 5 questioned about the views of participants on using reasoners for research. Figure 2 indicated that most people find the difficulty modest. Out of 21 valid responses of question 3b), 18 of them were valid. 57.1% agreed that learning a reasoner takes some time. 71.4% admitted that some mathematical, logic, computer science knowledge was required to use a reasoner for research. 42.9% of the participants have been introduced to using reasoners for research in their university education (so far). In comparison, 9.5% of them stated that they have not been introduced (yet). 38.1% complained that some reasoners lack of documentation or tutorials, which made it hard to learn. Question 3c) studied the usability of reasoners in comparison with traditional pen and paper approach. It received 18 valid responses. 8 of them agreed that this approach speed up problem solving process in general and makes research easier. In comparison, 3 of them thought it could make some research problems even more complicated. Half of them admitted that it was the only approach for some research problems. Another two indicated that this approach was not applicable in many domains. One suggested that this approach was not applied in a large scale yet. Question 3d) got 24 responses (Figure 3). The average for this question was 3.58, indicating that the proofs generated by reasoners were well trusted. The last question (Figure 4) was compulsory for all participants. A bit less than 30% of them did not see themselves using reasoners more for research. Only just over ten percent of the participants were more certain that they will use reasoners more in research in the future. The overall average is 2.3. For those 16 participants who have used reasoners for research, the average was slightly higher (3.1).

How hard do you find it to learn using reasoners for research? (21 responses)

Figure 2: Reply Distribution of Question 3a)
How much do you trust the proofs or other forms of results by reasoners? (24 responses)

Figure 3: Reply Distribution of Question 3d)
Will you use reasoners more in your research in the future? (76 responses)

Figure 4: Reply Distribution of Question 3e)

4 Discussion

The hypothesis of the survey was that the majority had little or no knowledge about this approach while a minority had a limited amount of knowledge and experience. The survey results confirmed the hypothesis. Among those who had some experience using reasoners for research, the overall average about their willingness to use reasoner for their future research was 3.1, which was not supportive enough to conclude that using reasoners was getting more popular (among students). Both UvA and VU offered a good amount of courses using, or at least introducing reasoners. In UvA, courses such as *Knowledge Representation*, *Knowledge Representation on the Web* and *Functional Specification of Algorithms* included assignments or projects using reasoners as part of the course. Other courses such as *Computational Complexity* and *Combinatorics with Computer Science Applications* were highly likely to introduce the use of reasoners for some research tasks. For Master's students of VU, *Protocol Validation*², *Logical Verification* and *Term Rewriting Systems* were available courses where reasoners are introduced. Overall, at least 9.0% of those have learnt using a reasoner from courses by the universities. Considering some of the courses were compulsory for some Master's students, this rate showed that this approach is still to be promoted. However, in both university's mathematics master programme, there was no course using reasoners of any kind as far as the author knew from the description of courses on the websites. This was reflected in the result, only two out of nine mathematics Master's students

²This course was available to many students in UvA also.

had some basic awareness about this approach. No mathematics PhD student had awareness about this approach. As for doctoral level, many research groups' work took advantage of reasoners. In VU, the Knowledge Representation Reasoning group and the Theoretical Computer Science group were actively involved in developing and using reasoners. As for UvA, ILLC was a major player of logic research. However, there were too few responses from PhD students in ILLC to conclude anything. The Qualitative Reasoning Group of the Theory of Computer Science section was the major user of reasoners in the Informatics Institute. As a consequence of active research in using and developing reasoners, VU and UvA computer science PhD students' knowledge about reasoners was better than that of Master's students and some were involved developing reasoners. The survey also showed that ITPs are less popular than ATPs in general. There were more classes of research activities involving automated provers and many were specialised for certain tasks only (e.g. MAXSAT). In comparison, ITPs were mostly used for proving theorems. The study also showed that, proving mathematical and logical theorem may no longer be limited to first order or higher order theorem provers, etc. Type inference systems, ASP solvers and SAT solvers were also being used for such activities. SAT solver was the most popular reasoner due to its fundamental role in the development of reasoners and assignments in courses. However, no participant had experience with SMT solver. Instead, a more specialised class of reasoners, MAXSAT solvers, were relatively familiar to students. Taking into consideration that two of the three who have used MAXSAT solvers have also used SAT solvers, a possible reason could be that MAXSAT implements similar functions as SAT solvers and of similar use. Another output worth addressing was that inductive reasoners were very popular among both logic and computer science Master's and PhD students. As far as the course category showed, there was no course about inductive reasoning at Master's level. The best guess is that Prolog was taught as a part of their Bachelor's education and it was natural for some to use some Prolog programs as inductive reasoners. Another factor could be that Amsterdam had a big Prolog community. However, the actual reason remained unclear to the author.

It was shown that the majority agreed that there was an overhead of learning if this approach was chosen. Many agreed that learning reasoners took time and required specific knowledge. ATP Users usually need to specify one problem to the reasoner. This process is called encoding. The output of the reasoner is then decoded to meaningful solutions of the original problem. This learning process can be time consuming and the encoding and decoding process can be confusing to many. However, this encode-solve-decode process is a general pattern for many automated reasoners. Once one reasoner is learnt, learning and using the others are of similar style. A barrier is that many reasoners lack of documentation or user manual, which makes some participants suffer while learning. No participant admitted that mailing lists help understanding reasoners. In fact, the mailing list of a reasoner is usually a platform where developers and users help each other. Considering only one participant have experience developing a reasoner, it was not representative enough to conclude anything valuable. In addition, over half of those who have used reasoners agreed that it is the only approach for some problems, which emphasised the status of the use of reasoners in research.

There were several drawbacks of this survey. Question 1b) and ac) may be merged. It would be better to study the source of knowledge about this approach (i.e. if it was taught in a course as a separate question (see Question 2a) and 3b)). As for Question 3e), the question itself suggested that participants suppose to use reasoners more, which can be misleading. Also it was compulsory, which made little sense to those who did not even know what a reasoner is. Following this work, future research may include more studies about senior researchers and details about user experience and trends. The results showed that most students, especially the mathematics students lack of knowledge of this approach. As reasoners get more usable and powerful, introducing reasoner-aid research may be done systematically in some Master's courses or even Bachelor's courses.

5 Conclusion

This paper provides a summary of recent advances of interactive and automated reasoning and reasoner-aid research. Although there were several aspects to be improved in the questionnaire, the survey results successfully provided a general understanding of the popularity of reasoner-aid research among Master and PhD students in UvA and VU. The research results confirmed the hypothesis that most students lack of the knowledge of this approach and a minority have some limited experience.

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A Survey Questions

Due to the limit of space, a summary of the survey organised by section is as follows. A copy of the complete survey is online at <http://goo.gl/forms/kOTOV38HIPTfJ98e2>.

1. General Information
 - (a) What is your education status?
 - (b) If you are a PhD student (promovendus or promovenda), what is your main research area?
 - (c) If you are a Master’s student, what is your programme?

2. Participants’ knowledge about this approach
 - (a) How much do you know about using reasoners of any kind to assist research of any field at all?
 - I have never heard about reasoners of any kind
 - I know reasoners but I have never heard that they can be used to assist research
 - I have some awareness about how a reasoner could help
 -
 - (b) What kind of reasoners have you used?
 - SAT solver (for satisfiability problems)
 - SMT solver (for satisfiability modulo theories problems)
 -
 - (c) What kind of research activities have you conducted that takes advantage of these reasoners?
 - prove mathematical or logical theorems
 - verify existing proofs
 -

3. Participants’ view about this approach
 - (a) How hard do you find it to learn using reasoners for research?
 - (b) Check all statements that apply to you concerning learning the use of reasoners for research
 - It takes some time to learn.
 - It requires some mathematical, logical or computer science knowledge.
 -
 - (c) What do you think about this approach in terms of usability, compared with traditional pen and paper approach?
 - It can make some research problems even more complicated.
 - It makes research easier and accelerates the problem solving process in general.
 -
 - (d) How much do you trust the proofs or other forms of results by reasoners?
 - (e) Will you use reasoners more in your research in the future?